

From Textual Search to Geodetic Search: Enhancing Library Retrieval Systems

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Abstract

Information retrieval in libraries, regardless of their size or type, has primarily focused on textual search, neglecting the significant advancements in digital information representation and retrieval such as image search, multimedia retrieval, multilingual retrieval, integrated discovery search, and other related areas like geodetic search. Geodetic search refers to a type of search functionality that incorporates geographic coordinates and spatial data in information retrieval systems. It utilizes coordinates, such as latitude and longitude, to identify and retrieve relevant data associated with particular places or regions and can be particularly useful in domains where location plays a significant role in retrieval, such as documentary resources on geography, geology, environmental sciences, urban planning, and travel. This paper aims to augment the information retrieval capabilities of a typical library retrieval system by integrating geodetic search functionalities. The proposed prototype framework utilizes VuFind, an open-source library discovery software based on Solr, as the retrieval system. It incorporates Leaflet, an open-source JavaScript library for interactive maps, and OpenStreetMap as the cartographic data provider, which is available under the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL). The prototype deploys the indexing of coordinate data (longitude, latitude and bounding box) for a given set of MARC records using the tag 034, subfields d, e, f, g, and h (specific to different place names of India) in Koha, and then extends the geodetic search facility in VuFind by harvesting indexed MARC records from Koha.

Keywords: Geodetic search, Bounding box data, Geocoordinate indexing, Map-based retrieval, Koha, VuFind, Leaflet, Nominatim, OpenStreetMap

1. Introduction

In developing countries, academic libraries are gradually moving away from multiple retrieval systems and adopting single-window search systems through the implementation of open-source library discovery systems. Particularly in Indian academic libraries, Online Public Access Catalogues (OPACs) are being replaced by library discovery systems that manage a centralized index encompassing both internal and external knowledge objects. The internal knowledge objects consist of locally organized resources that can be retrieved globally, while the external knowledge objects include subscribed and open access resources that are not typically part of the local retrieval system. These library discovery systems not only provide a unified access point to all library materials but also offer additional functionalities such as full-text indexing, custom search prompts, deduplication of resources, and the FRBRized display of retrieved results. They can also integrate authority search systems, employ query-forwarding mechanisms, and enable browsing using various selected keys such as call numbers, document types, and license types. However, the most notable feature of a library discovery system is its ability to incorporate information visualization techniques into the retrieval interface, surpassing the limitations of a purely textual search system. One such visual search

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interface is geodetic search, which falls under the domain of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and serves as a land-information system.

Geodetic search utilizes a mathematical framework to spatially reference all land data and determine locations on the Earth's surface (Abresch et al., 2008). This mechanism enables users to go beyond text-only search and facilitates the effective retrieval of documents and datasets focused on specific places or geographic names, such as resources in the fields of geography, mineralogy, geology, and travel guides. In the bibliographic domain, a geodetic search framework should incorporate additional elements including standard mechanisms for describing and encoding geocoordinate values (such as latitude/longitude or boundary values) associated with the places discussed in the documents, mechanisms for indexing geocoordinate values, integration of geocoordinate values with the utilized map service, and the exposure of geodetic datasets in the search interface to filter search results (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2018).

2. Literature Review

In 2006, a notable book on georeferencing (Hill, 2006) emphasized the potential of geographic information retrieval for bibliographic resources. It also demonstrated how geocoordinate data values can be described in various metadata schemas, including MARC. In 2008, an edited book (Abresch et al., 2008) took a systematic approach to explore the management of geospatial data in library retrieval systems. One chapter in this book (Chapter IV) specifically addressed the encoding of geocoordinate data values in MARC 21 bibliographic and authority formats, RDA, and MARCXML. The authors highlighted the crucial need for tag 034 encoding and advocated for the exploration of automated methods to gather geocoordinate data for tag 034 (Hanson & Heron, 2008). The possibilities of autogenerating geocoordinate values emerged with the advent of LOD technologies, LOD datasets, and open-source data wrangling software. Examples of research in this area include a script for reconciling authority datasets from LODs (Harlow, 2015), the development of LOD for a geographic name authority file for a specific country (Ryan et al., 2015), merging authority data for a nationwide library network into LOD-formatted datasets (Bensmann et al., 2017), and a case study on using OpenRefine as a tool to gather geocoordinate values and convert them to MARC formatted records (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2021). At the VuFind summit in 2016, Leila Gonzales (Gonzales, 2016) showcased mechanisms for indexing MARC-formatted bibliographic records with geocoordinate values in Tag 034 using Solr, the backend text retrieval engine of VuFind. She also demonstrated the development of map-based retrieval, incorporating Google Maps alongside textual search capabilities. Subsequently, Gonzales developed geodetic search interfaces for the American Geosciences Institute, specifically for the Antarctic Bibliography (1950-2011) and state geological surveys (American Geosciences Institute, 2019, 2021). She proposed further improvements to the indexing framework to enhance retrieval efficiency for geographic search (Gonzales, 2017).

However, most of these research works rely on bibliographic datasets that already contain geocoordinate data values either in authority datasets or through manual population of tag 034. This poses a challenge for libraries in developing countries, as bibliographic records without geocoordinate data values cannot be effectively utilized to explore geodetic search mechanisms. Thus, finding alternative methods to populate geocoordinate data values in bibliographic records becomes crucial for offering additional retrieval capabilities to end-users.

The authors of this research study first reported a mechanism for the automatic development of a geographic name authority file for India, ranging from states to community blocks, in MARC 21 authority data format using data wrangling techniques (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2022). The present research report discusses how that geoname authority datasets can be utilized in an ILS (here Koha) as geographic name authority file, and then shows how those records can be harvested in an open source library discovery system (here VuFind) to develop a geodetic search interface in addition to textual search.

3. Geocoordinate Indexing

The differentiation between place and space holds significant importance. Place represents a cultural concept, while space pertains to the physical aspect. Cultural resources primarily focus on places rather than spaces. Place names often exhibit multiple interpretations, ambiguity, and susceptibility to changes influenced by various socio-cultural factors. For example, places can undergo modifications through alterations in names or boundaries. On the other hand, space is a relatively modern concept characterized by greater stability. Places encompass spaces, enabling the establishment of connections between two or more places through a shared system of spatial description. This process is commonly referred to as georeferencing. Georeferencing relies on the universally accepted system of latitude and longitude, which provides a standardized framework for describing locations. Bounding box data, which consists of coordinates defining rectangular boundaries around a region of interest in a two-dimensional space, is often incorporated within this system. Georeferencing plays a crucial role in visualizing both the location and spatial relationships of objects or regions through map displays. This facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the spatial aspects associated with cultural and physical phenomena (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2018).

In the realm of bibliographic data, the MARC 21 family of standards serves as the global de facto standard. This family includes a total of five coordinated standards, with the MARC 21 format for bibliographic data and the MARC 21 format for authority data being the most commonly utilized standards in Indian libraries. Integrated Library Systems (ILS), and library discovery systems seamlessly integrate these two standards, allowing for real-time linking of resources in end-users' retrieval interfaces. Establishing a connection between bibliographic data and authority data is crucial for controlling index terms or headings, such as author headings or subject index terms, in order to enhance retrieval efficiency in keyword search environments. Figure 1 illustrates an example of the linking mechanism between bibliographic and authority data in the Koha ILS, showcasing how access points in a bibliographic record (1XX, 6XX, 7XX, and 8XX in MARC 21 bibliographic format) automatically generate corresponding authority records (with 1XX, 4XX, and 5XX tags) in MARC 21 authority format through the linking mechanism.

There are three essential parameters for encoding geocoordinate data values in the tag 034 of MARC 21 bibliographic and authority formats. Firstly, it involves specifying whether the geocoordinate data represents an area or a point on the Earth's surface. Secondly, it entails selecting the appropriate style for representing the geocoordinate data values, with MARC 21 allowing four different styles. Lastly, it involves determining the rendering styles for geopolitical divisions. The tag 034 is present in both the bibliographic and authority formats, sharing identical subfield codes except for 034 \$a - Category of scale (NR), which is exclusive to the bibliographic format.

Figure 1. Linking mechanism of bibliographic and authority data in Koha (source: Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2021)

The designated subfields for encoding the coordinates are as follows: \$d - Coordinates - westernmost longitude (NR), \$e - Coordinates - easternmost longitude (NR), \$f - Coordinates - northernmost latitude (NR), and \$g - Coordinates - southernmost latitude (NR). These subfields encode the four coordinates of a geographical object, place, geopolitical division, or geophysical entity, following the sequence of West-East-North-South (WENS). Another important rule for encoding in the tag 034 relates to the style of representation for geocoordinate data. For instance, geocoordinate values can be represented in decimal degrees using the format: hddd.ddddd (hemisphere-degrees.decimal degrees) as specified in MARC 21 standards for both authority and bibliographic formats. The hemispheres are denoted by letter codes (N=North, S=South, E=East, W=West), or alternatively, “+” for N and E and “-” for S and W (with the plus sign “+” being optional). The encoding rules also accommodate other formats such as degrees/minutes/seconds (hddmmss), decimal minutes (hddmm.mmmm), and decimal seconds (hddmmss.sss). Examples illustrating the expression of geocoordinate values in the tag 034, using the two most commonly employed styles in both bibliographic and authority formats, are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Representation of Geocoordinate Data in two Different Styles

Decimal degrees (Bounding box data)	Degrees-minutes-seconds (Bounding box data)
Place: Bagda - a community development block under 24 Paraganas (North) district in West Bengal, India	Place: Bagda - a community development block under 24 Paraganas (North) district in West Bengal, India
034 \$dE088.694873 \$eE088.995886 \$fN023.107796 \$gN023.256612	034 \$dE0884141 \$eE0885945 \$fN0230628 \$gN0231523

(source: Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2022)

4. Developing Geographic Name Authority Datasets

Geographic name authority datasets play a crucial role in document retrieval when geographic locations, encompassing both space and place, are key components. The inclusion of latitude, longitude and bounding box data (encompassing westernmost, easternmost, northernmost, and southernmost geocoordinate values) in such datasets holds the potential to facilitate map-based retrieval systems within library retrieval through geodetic search mechanisms. However, it is noteworthy that the coverage and extent of information provided by global geographic name authority datasets (such as LCNF, FAST, VIAF, and Wikidata) significantly diminish as one moves from the country/state level to more granular levels such as districts, towns, and villages in Asian countries. As reported by the authors of this research work in an earlier research study, in LCNF, while there is complete coverage of Indian states, the coverage of Indian place names at the town/village level is only 3%. In addition to this inadequate coverage of Indian place names (as depicted in Table 2), global geographic name authority datasets also lack the presence of geocoordinate values in content designation, specifically within Tag 034 - Coded Cartographic Mathematical Data (R). Consequently, these datasets are not optimally suitable for the development of geodetic search mechanisms.

Table 2. Coverage of Indian Geo-Administrative units in global authority datasets

Entity	Numbers	Indian Geographic Names in Global Authority Datasets			Wikidata
		LCNF	FAST	VIAF	
States and Union Territories	28 States 8 UTs	Match: 36(100%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 00	Match: 36(100%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 00	Match: 36(100%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 00	Match: 36(100%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 00
Districts	737	Match: 570 (77%) Suggestion: 48 No match: 118	Match: 515 (77%) Suggestion: 23 No match: 198	Match: 540 (73%) Suggestion: 02 No match: 194	Match: 736 (99%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 00
Subdistricts	6907	Match: 1763(25%) Suggestion: 01 No match: 5098	Match: 1796 (26%) Suggestion: 01 No match: 5065	Match: 2096 (30%) Suggestion: 01 No match: 4765	Match: 5390 (78%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 1472
Blocks	7211	Match: 1725(24%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 5493	Match: 1828 (25%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 5390	Match: 2067 (29%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 5151	Match: 5610 (78%) Suggestion: 00 No match: 1608

(source: Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2022)

The geodetic search mechanism requires geographic name authority datasets that contain accurately encoded geocoordinate data values. However, currently, no India-specific datasets are available at the national or international levels to fulfill this requirement. To address this limitation, the authors have utilized a solution based on their earlier work (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2022). This work presents a mechanism for constructing MARC 21 formatted geographic name authority datasets specifically for Indian place names. The process begins with obtaining an authenticated place names file from the Local Government Directory (LGD), Ministry of Panchayati Raj, Government of India. This file, available in CSV format, encompasses a comprehensive list of Indian place names at various levels

throughout the entire country (Figure 2). It can be downloaded under the Open Database License (ODbL) from the LGD website (<https://lgdirectory.gov.in/>).

1. No. of States/Union Territories (UTs)	36
2. No. of Districts	765
3. No. of Sub-Districts	7077
4. No. of Development Blocks	7245
5. No. of Villages	664396
a. No. of Inhabited Village	648422
b. No. of Un-inhabited Villages	15206
c. No. of Forest Villages	768
d. No. of Villages (Rural)	641066
e. No. of Villages (Urban)	13704
6. No. of Rural Local Bodies	262688
a. No. of District Panchayats	665
b. No. of Block Panchayats	6697
c. No. of Gram Panchayats	255326
7. No. of Traditional Local Bodies	16145
a. No. of District Level Councils	14
b. No. of Intermediate Level Councils	2288
c. No. of Village Level Councils	13843
8. No. of Urban Local Bodies	4853
a. No. of Municipal Corporations	255
b. No. of Municipalities	1863
c. No. of Town Panchayats	2411
9. No. of Cantonment Boards	59
10. No. of Parliament Constituencies	765
11. No. of Assembly Constituencies	765

Figure 2. Coverage in LGD (source: lgdirectory.gov.in)

The said research work demonstrates how the LGD dataset can be enhanced by retrieving geospatial data and other relevant datasets from open access sources. Various data wrangling tools and techniques are employed to gather and integrate the geocoordinate data values into the geographic name authority file for Indian place names. This process enables the creation of a comprehensive dataset with geocoordinate information, enhancing the usability and functionality of the geodetic search mechanism. The MARC-formatted (MARC 21 authority data format) datasets (from state to community development block levels) developed by the authors in their earlier research work (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2022) by using OpenRefine as data wrangling software includes all states and UTs (36), districts (765) and subdistricts (7077), and community development blocks (7245). Figure 3 shows how district names of India (765 in number) are converted into MARC authority data format in four columns (RecordNumber|Tags|Indicators|Content) in OpenRefine to make it compatible for the MarcEdit software for further processing. It gathers geocoordinate data values (Tag 034) from Nominatim (nominatim.openstreetmap.org), See references (Tag 451) from Wikidata (wikidata.org), Source Data Found (Tag 670) from Wikidata, Established Heading Linking Entry (Tag 751) from LC, VIAF and FAST.

	RecordNumber	Tags	Indicators	Content
334.	15	LDR		nz a22 n 4500
335.	15	003		IN-KyU
336.	15	034	\	\$dE078.703393\$eE078.943977\$IN011.322457\$gN011.134402
337.	15	043	\	\$aa-ii---
338.	15	151	\	\$aIndia\$aPerambalur (District)
339.	15	451	\	\$aPerambalur district
340.	15	451	\	\$aপেরাম্বলুর জিলা
341.	15	451	\	\$aপেরাম্বলুর জেলা
342.	15	451	\	\$aபெரம்பலூர் மாவட்டம்
343.	15	670	\	\$aGeoNames [algorithmically matched]\$blat/long:11.272N /8.8738E\$uhttp://www.geonames.org/627071
344.	15	670	\	\$aOpenStreetMap [algorithmically matched]\$bbox (wens):E078.703393 E078.943977 N011.322457 N011.134402\$uhttps://relation/10322350
345.	15	670	\	\$aWikidata [algorithmically matched]\$bdescription;district of Tamil Nadu, India\$uhttps://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
346.	15	670	\	\$aWikidata [algorithmically matched]\$bdescription;தமிழ்நாடு கா ஜিলা\$uhttps://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
347.	15	670	\	\$aWikidata [algorithmically matched]\$bdescription;தமிழ்நாட்டின் ஜেলা\$uhttps://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
348.	15	670	\	\$aWikidata [algorithmically matched]\$bdescription;தமிழ்நாட்டின் ஜেলা\$uhttps://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
349.	15	670	\	\$aWikidata [algorithmically matched]\$bdescription;தமிழ்நாட்டின் ஜেলা\$uhttps://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
350.	15	751	\	\$2Wikidata\$aPerambalur district\$0(wikidata)Q15186\$0https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q15186
351.	15	751	\	\$2LCS\$aPerambalur (India : District)\$0(DL.C)j2021241322\$0http://id.loc.gov/authorities/names/n2021241322
352.	15	751	\	\$2VIAF\$aপেরাম্বলুর জিলা\$0(viaf)238669527\$0https://viaf.org/viaf/238669527

Figure 3. From place names to MARC records in OpenRefine

5. Objectives and Research Questions

The title of this paper accurately captures its overarching goal, and discussion in the earlier sections sets the tone of the objectives and the corresponding research questions (RQs) of the present study. However, the main objective centres around a single RQ – how the geographic name authority datasets for India as developed for different levels from state to community development block can further be utilized in enhancing search features of a library retrieval system. The specific objectives, and the related RQs may be crystallized as follows:

Objectives

To investigate geospatial search mechanisms specifically tailored for locating documentary resources related to a particular geographical area, with districts of India serving as the case study.

To devise improved searching and browsing capabilities for documentary resources, giving significant consideration to the role of place names in retrieval processes.

To design an interactive map-based retrieval system that complements the traditional textual search approach within library search systems.

Related RQ

How MARC-compatible datasets as developed by an earlier work of the authors can be extended to use further in Koha as geographic name authority file?

How the bibliographic records as indexed in Koha by using the imported India-specific geographic name authority file can be harvested into and tuned for geographic search in VuFind?

How to configure VuFind to support browsing and searching by geocoordinate values and to select a given geo-administrative area to pinpoint searching?

6. Indexing in Koha

Before the file becomes compatible for importing into Koha, the MARC-formatted file must be fine tuned to ensure smooth interoperability. The steps involved in finalizing the geographic name authority data file, which can be referred to as a completed MARC 21 based authority file, are as follows:

- (a) Export the finalized data structure of authority records from Openrefine in 'tsv' (tab-separated values) format;
- (b) Import the 'tsv' file into MarcEdit (version 7.3 is utilized for this purpose);
- (c) Remove any blank lines present in the records;
- (d) Add the 001 field (Control Number) with the prefix 'inkyu-<level code>' to all records. The prefix 'inkyu' represents the normalized MARC organization code for Kalyani University, while five level codes ('stu' for states & UTs, 'dst' for districts, 'sds' for sub-districts, 'cdb' for community development blocks, and 'ppl' for populated places like towns and villages) are created for local use. It should be noted that the prefix may vary for other agencies based on their MARC organization code;
- (e) Include the 005 field (date and time of the latest transaction) following the prescribed format of `yyyymmddhhmmss`, as per MARC 21 standards;
- (f) Add the 008 field (fixed-length data elements) with the default value '230531ia|fcz||a||a|| d', conforming to the MARC 21 format for authority data. The first six character positions represent the date of creation in `yymmdd` format; and
- (g) Save the file in 'mrc' format, which will generate the Leader for all authority records, effectively transforming the authority dataset into a finalized product ready for distribution and use in Indian libraries.

This dataset now can be imported into an Integrated Library System (ILS) to populate the 034 and 651 tags of the bibliographic format. Furthermore, the datasets can be implemented to facilitate geodetic search based on the geocoordinate values available in subfields (\$d\$e\$f\$g) of tag 034. Finally, the authority datasets corresponding to the four geoadministrative levels (state & UTs - 36, districts - 765, sub-districts - 7077, community development blocks - 7245) are merged using the MARCJoin utility of MarcEdit. This process generates a single consolidated file that includes all the geographic name authority records, covering the four geo-administrative divisions. The inherent value of authority datasets lies in their utilization within an Integrated Library System (ILS) during cataloging processes, specifically for managing name variants and subject access points. Geographic name authority datasets are no exception to this rule. Hence, the true assessment of the effectiveness of the geographic name authority dataset for India, developed using the methodology described in Section 6, can only be achieved if it can be successfully imported into an ILS. In this case, the Koha ILS, a widely adopted advanced open-source system, has been selected as the platform for evaluation. Furthermore, it is imperative that the dataset seamlessly integrates and establishes real-time links with bibliographic data during the cataloging workflow. This integration and functionality within the ILS serve as the ultimate measure to determine the practicality and utility of the geographic name authority dataset for India (see Figure 4).

The screenshot displays the Koha authority plugin interface. On the left, the MARC record editor shows tag 651 with the following fields: Authority record control number or standard number (4), Source of heading or term (9 (RLIN) 520), Geographic name (India), and Geographic subdivision (Birbhum (District)). On the right, the search results pane shows the following table:

Summary	Heading type	Used	Get it!	Other action
Geographic Name: India Birbhum (District) used for/see from: India Birabhūma (District) India Birbhum Birbhum district বীরভূম জিলা বীরভূম জেলা ബിർഭൂം ജില്ല	Geographic Name	1 times	+ Choose	Edit authority

Figure 4. Indexing geocoordinate values in Koha

7. Geodetic Search in VuFind

The implementation of a geodetic search mechanism within the bibliographic domain, also known as geographic search or GIS-enabled search, necessitates the presence of geocoordinate values in bibliographic records. These values can take the form of latitude & longitude coordinates indicating the position of a specific point on Earth, or they can be represented as geocoordinate boundaries (bounding box data). The successful deployment of such a mechanism requires several additional requirements to be fulfilled, including: extracting longitudes and latitudes, accommodating repeatable geocoordinate values within a single document, integrating geocoordinate data with the chosen map service, and exposing geodetic datasets within the search interface to facilitate search result filtering (Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2018; Mukhopadhyay & Mukhopadhyay, 2021). In essence, the inclusion of a geodetic search mechanism in a library discovery system enhances retrieval capabilities by enabling map-based searching in addition to traditional textual searches. The fundamental condition for effective geodetic search lies in the availability of geocoordinate values within bibliographic records, specifically within the designated subfields (\$d\$e\$f\$g) of the MARC 21 tag 034 (both bibliographic and authority data formats). By utilizing a geographic name authority dataset, Koha ensures that all bibliographic records cataloged in the system are automatically populated with geocoordinate values sourced from linked authority records. In the case of VuFind (Version 9.0), with minimal adjustments, it can be seamlessly integrated

with Leaflet, an open-source JavaScript library used for displaying interactive maps in the search interface. This integration allows VuFind to support geocoordinate indexing through designated fields (such as `long_lat`, `long_lat_label`, `long_latdisplay`, and `location_geo`) within Apache-Solr, the underlying open-source text retrieval engine of VuFind (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Geodetic indexing & search framework in VuFind (source: VuFind Wiki)
 The conjunction of geodetic search requirements and the corresponding features of VuFind creates an opportune environment for exploring geodetic search capabilities using geographic name authority datasets for Indian place names.

Figure 6. Geodetic search in VuFind

This approach demonstrates that geodetic search can serve as an additional feature to facilitate visual search alongside text-based retrieval. Notable features supported by this mechanism include displaying documents based on default geocoordinate values, zooming in and out functions within the map selection, combining textual search with GIS search, drawing search boxes by freely selecting coordinates on the displayed map, indicating the number of available titles within a given geographical area, and providing map navigation for locating documents related to a specific geographical region (Figure 6). Furthermore, the detailed view of retrieved records can include a dedicated “Map View” tab alongside “Holdings,” showcasing all geographic locations covered in the respective book.

8. Conclusion

The application of data carpentry, aligned with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, has significantly influenced library workflows worldwide. This case study serves as an example of leveraging open access data sources and open source data wrangling tools to develop large-scale authority datasets, which can be made available as Linked Open Data (LOD) or may be downloaded in suitable bibliographic formats. The availability of India-specific authority datasets will undoubtedly enhance the cataloguing environment for Indian libraries. It is evident from discussion and demonstration that the availability of feature-rich open source software and open access data sources has made it considerably easier to develop a comprehensive geographic name authority dataset from scratch. Furthermore, this research unveils the mechanisms through which such an authority dataset can be utilized in cataloguing to support collocation and enhance the finding function including the support for map-based search interfaces for documents where retrieval by place names is of utmost importance.

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